

A new perspective on frequency control in conventional and future interconnected power systems

Tomislav Baškarad^{*}, Ninoslav Holjevac, Igor Kuzle

University of Zagreb Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, Zagreb, Croatia

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ABSTRACT

In the interconnected power systems, the frequency change during disturbances may manifest differently in certain areas in the initial moments after the disturbance. Due to wave propagation, generating units located in distant areas contribute to primary frequency control (PFC) with a certain time delay. To address this issue, this study presents a novel primary frequency control (PFC) mechanism that enables generators in remote areas to adjust their output power before the disturbance wave propagates to that area. This mechanism leverages the use of PMU systems to enable early power adjustments. The proposed PFC mechanism is applicable to both conventional interconnected power systems and future systems with a significant share of converter-based technologies. The effectiveness of the method is demonstrated through simulations conducted on a two-area power system model, showing a 15 % reduction in maximum frequency deviation compared to the conventional method. This improvement results in a lower frequency nadir, offering the potential for a decrease of frequency nadir of up to 0.2 Hz when the disturbance causes the frequency drop to 49 Hz.

1. Introduction

Frequency control (FC) is one of the primary measures used to maintain a stable and secure power system. In particular, primary frequency control (PFC) and secondary frequency control (SFC) are essential components of FC. In power system models, PFC and SFC are often studied in single-area power systems, which assume that all generator units in the system operate at a single common frequency. However, this assumption is not always realistic, as power systems consist of multiple interconnected areas that can operate at different frequencies during a disturbance due to the wave disturbance propagation time. Therefore, to investigate power system frequency dynamics more accurately, multi-area power system models are used. A multi-area power system consists of various interconnected single areas, and the FC in a multi-area system regulates not only the frequency of the system, but also the change in the tie-line power flow between the areas.

Unlike a single-area power system model, a multi-area power system model enables the investigation of phenomena during which not all generators will experience a simultaneous change in frequency. The cause of this phenomenon can be found in the wave disturbance propagation time, which is the time required for a frequency disturbance to propagate through the power system and reach its distanced segments.

This delay in frequency response is due to the wave propagation characteristics of the transmission lines, and it varies depending on the distance between the generators and the disturbance location. For example, if a large generator suddenly trips offline, the frequency of the grid will drop. However, more distant generators will respond with a certain delay during PFC activation due to the wave disturbance propagation time. According to research conducted on the US power grid [1,2], it has been found that in response to a sudden loss of significant generation at a bus located at one end of the system, it may take up to 2.5 s for the frequency of buses located at the other end of the system to decrease below 59.95 Hz. The disturbance propagation effect was observable even in small power systems such as the Croatian power system [3].

Recent developments in Phasor Measurement Unit (PMU) technology have made it possible to monitor the state of the power systems in real-time. PMUs can provide information about the state of the power system, such as the frequency, voltage, and phase angle, with a high degree of accuracy and time resolution. By taking advantage of PMU synchronized measurements, power system frequency stability can be significantly improved. The basic idea of this research paper is to utilize the advantages of fast PMU measurements to enable distant generators in the system to receive information about the frequency change faster

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: tomislav.baskarad@fer.hr (T. Baškarad).

Fig. 1. A proposed method concept illustration.

than it would take for the disturbance to propagate to them. This approach could potentially allow generators to start the power change earlier, improving the overall stability of the power system.

1.1. Motivation

This research was inspired by real-life incidents [4–7] observed in interconnected power systems, where a delayed frequency drop in one area compared to another area was clearly noticeable. One such example is the Australian power system, which is divided into five interconnected areas connected by tie-lines. In May 2021, a generator trip in the Queensland (QLD) area led to a frequency drop that triggered under-frequency load shedding [4]. While the frequency started to decline immediately in the QLD area, there was a delay of approximately 0.7 s in the frequency drop observed in New South Wales (NSW). Another event occurred in the same month and year when a substation in Rogowiec, Poland, disconnected [5,6]. Between the Spain power system and the Poland power system, there are two additional power systems, Germany and France, and the frequency drop in Spain occurred approximately 1.5 s after the frequency drop in Poland. A recent event [7] further highlights the presence of delayed frequency drop between two interconnected power systems, namely the Norway and Sweden power systems, even with a relatively short interconnection tie-line. In June 2023, an unexpected disconnection of the North Sea Link (NSL) interconnector resulted in a frequency rise in the Nordic power system. The frequency rise was immediately experienced in the Norway power system, while in the Sweden power system, it was detected with a 0.5 s delay.

Motivated by these events, this research aims to investigate whether the frequency response can be improved by enabling generators in distant areas to respond earlier. Since some types of power plants, mainly hydroelectric power plants, require some time to change power due to water inertia, an earlier order to start changing power could result in arresting the frequency drop much faster. The analysis will be conducted on a typical two-area power system model, commonly used in numerous papers to study frequency responses of interconnected power systems.

To address this issue, using a phasor measurement unit (PMU) to detect frequency changes is proposed as PMUs have been already used in several applications, including real-time monitoring, control, and protection of power systems. This research aims to develop a system that can detect a frequency change and send data to distant generators in

real-time. The PMU measures the phase angle and amplitude of the voltage and current at a specific location on the network, making it possible to identify changes in the frequency in real-time. By providing real-time data to the distant generators, the system could enable the generators to respond more quickly to frequency changes. This would allow the generators to start changing power earlier before the disturbance wave propagates to them. The proposed method appears to be feasible based on empirical evidence from both theoretical research [1] and practical measurements [8], which demonstrate that wave disturbance propagation can persist for several seconds, while the average time delay between measurement and signal processing by the PMU device is less than 100 ms [9]. In summary, the slow wave propagation in power systems happens primarily due to the physical and electrical characteristics of the power grid, as well as its distributed nature. PMUs, on the other hand, are capable of quick transmission of measurement data using modern communication technologies. An illustration of proposed method concept is shown in Fig. 1. In the typical PMU system architecture, the first step involves the measurement of frequency using PMUs. These measurements are then collected and processed by a Phasor Data Concentrator (PDC) [10]. The PDC serves as a central hub for data management, where it combines and organizes the measurements from multiple PMUs. Alongside the PDC, various data services are employed to perform additional functions such as signal processing and filtering, event detection etc. Finally, based on the processed data, desired actions and control decisions can be implemented to ensure the efficient operation of the power system. In the context of this study, one such function is the transmission of frequency information from the area where the disturbance occurred to the generators located in other areas.

Therefore, in the event of a disturbance occurring in one area, the frequency signal of that area (dashed blue line on Fig. 1) could be transmitted to the generators in another area, allowing for faster power change. Another benefit of the proposed method is its minimal infrastructure requirements. The only necessary component is a switch with two inputs: one for conventional frequency measurements taken at the generator terminal, and another for PMU measurements. This simplicity makes the implementation of the proposed method highly feasible.

1.2. Literature review

In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in the use of

PMUs to improve the stability of power systems. Several research papers have discussed the various applications of PMUs in power systems. One study [11] proposed a method for online prediction of transient stability or rotor angle stability, which was shown to be capable of making precise predictions of the dynamic behavior of the system within 200 ms. Another paper [12] proposed a method that utilized PMUs to give detailed predictions of the dynamic behavior of an individual generator in case of system instability.

PMUs have also been used for interconnected system frequency control, with one method proposed in a study [13] estimating the value of the inertia constant of the system in real-time, which is crucial information since the frequency response of the system is largely dependent on this parameter. The effectiveness of using PMUs in primary and secondary frequency regulation has been evaluated in several papers. The use of PMUs in primary frequency regulation [14] was found to be an effective method even when communication system delays were considered, while their application in secondary frequency regulation for island systems [15] showed an overall improvement in frequency response, reducing frequency power oscillations. However, to ensure the proper functioning of PMU methods, researchers have developed methodologies [16,17] to avoid or handle situations in the presence of intentional or unintentional bad measured data and various uncertainties. These methodologies can detect bad data and eliminate them to ensure that PMU methods work satisfactorily in short circuit [16] or frequency control [17] analyses.

Despite the growing deployment of PMU devices in power systems worldwide, there are still systems where the installation of a significant number of PMUs is impractical due to the associated high costs. To address this challenge, there are research activities that has been conducted on the optimal PMU placement techniques [18] that enable the reduction of the number of required PMUs while maintaining the desired level of system observability.

Improvement of frequency control in interconnected systems can be achieved through the development of various types of controllers. Recent works [19–21] have mainly focused on the integration of renewable energy sources and proposed new algorithms for SFC controllers. In [19], a SFC controller is proposed to reduce frequency oscillations and tie-line power flow under increased wind power penetration. Paper [20] proposes a method to reduce power flow oscillations in interconnection systems by providing virtual inertia with wind turbines. In addition to improving frequency response in low-inertia systems, the method presented in [21] aims to improve the swing stability of rotor angle. Papers that do not consider renewable energy sources but still focus on FC, such as [22,23], mainly aim to reduce area control error or, generally speaking, improve the performance of secondary frequency regulation. Only a few studies focus on primary frequency regulation. The PFC controller presented in [24] was developed to minimize the effect of system parameter uncertainties, while the PFC controller developed in [25] was tested on the Scottish system model to evaluate the potential for providing fast frequency response. Both studies show a significant reduction in frequency nadir and ROCOF. An extensive review of various control strategies for FC in multi-area power systems can be found in [26]. The research outlined in paper [27] addresses the same issue as presented in this paper, aiming to facilitate quicker responses from generators in distant areas. However, there is a distinction in the approach. While paper [27] relies on an optimization process requiring generator and power system parameter data as input, this paper avoids complex optimization by utilizing PMUs to transmit real-frequency signals.

The literature survey reveals that several effective methods have been developed to enhance the stability of the system frequency. However, it also highlights several research gaps in the field of frequency control in interconnected power systems. While previous studies have made significant contributions by proposing different controllers for FC, there are specific areas that have received limited attention. One notable research gap pertains to the PFC aspect in interconnected power

systems. While a significant number of previous studies have primarily concentrated on SFC, including area control error reduction, and addressing challenges related to the integration of renewable energy sources, limited attention has been given to PFC which has largely been modelled based on conventional, well-established principles.

Furthermore, the time delay issue in frequency response across distant areas within interconnected power systems has not been extensively explored. The propagation of disturbance waves introduces delays in the frequency response of generators located in remote areas, which can adversely impact the overall system stability.

These research gaps create a need for innovative approaches that address PFC in the interconnected power systems and tackle the issue of time delays in frequency response. By taking advantage of the advanced capabilities of modern monitoring through PMUs, this paper presents a contribution to the field of interconnected power system frequency regulation by proposing a novel PFC framework. The proposed PFC mechanism, which allows generators in remote areas to respond earlier, directly addresses the identified gaps. By emphasizing the importance of early response and considering the unique characteristics of interconnected power systems, the proposed PFC mechanism offers a novel solution to improve the stability and performance of such systems. Moreover, if converter technologies such as batteries or PV systems are available in the system and capable of participating in frequency control, the proposed method becomes even more efficient.

1.3. Paper contribution

The contributions of this paper that build upon the drawbacks identified in the literature survey provided in the previous section are as follows:

- an innovative primary frequency control (PFC) mechanism for interconnected power systems;
- a new primary frequency control algorithm for converter-connected technologies based on tie-line power flow dynamics.

This paper is an extension of the paper published at the MED-POWER2022 conference [6] and is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an analysis of generating units power response; Section 3 describes the proposed PFC method for interconnected power systems; the results are presented in Section 4 and conclusions are given in Section 5.

2. Generating units power response

This section provides an analysis of the power response of specific types of conventional power plants to estimate the time it takes to respond to a frequency change. The power response of generating units during the primary frequency response phase can be analyzed by utilizing the following expression, which is written in the Laplace s-domain:

$$P(s) = -f(s) \cdot \frac{1}{R} H(s) \quad (1)$$

where $f(s)$ is a frequency deviation, R is a turbine droop coefficient [%], and $H(s)$ is a transfer function of generating units. To analyze power response of generating units in time domain, an inverse Laplace transform should be applied to Eq. (1). According to the convolution theorem, Eq. (1) can be rewritten as Eq. (2):

$$P(t) = -\frac{1}{R} \int_0^t f(x) \cdot H(t-x) dx \quad (2)$$

where f and H are time function of $f(s)$ and $H(s)$, respectively.

Here, the power response of three common generating unit types i.e., hydropower generating units, thermal generating unit with a reheat turbine, and thermal generating unit with non-reheat turbine is

Fig. 2. Power response of generating units.

analyzed. The transfer functions of the generating units are as follows [28]:

- The hydropower generating unit is represented with the governor, the transient droop compensation, and the turbine transfer functions, as denoted by Eq. (3):

$$H_{HPP}(s) = \frac{1}{1 + sT_G} \cdot \frac{1 + sT_R}{1 + s\left(\frac{R_T}{R_H}\right)T_R} \cdot \frac{1 - sT_W}{1 + 0.5sT_W} \quad (3)$$

- The thermal generating unit with a reheat steam turbine is represented with the governor and the turbine transfer functions, as denoted by Eq. (4):

$$H_{TTPP-rh}(s) = \frac{1}{1 + sT_G} \cdot \frac{1 + sF_{HP}T_{RH}}{(1 + sT_{CH})(1 + sT_{RH})} \quad (4)$$

- The thermal generating unit with non-reheat turbine is represented with the governor and the turbine transfer functions, as denoted by Eq. (5):

$$H_{TTPP-nrh}(s) = \frac{1}{1 + sT_G} \cdot \frac{1}{(1 + sT_{CH})} \quad (5)$$

By applying the inverse Laplace transform on any of the aforementioned expressions, the resultant function can be expressed as a linear combination of exponential functions, as denoted by Eq. (6):

$$\mathcal{L}^{-1}\{H_{HPP}, H_{TTPP-rh}, H_{TTPP-nrh}\} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_i \cdot e^{k_i t} \quad (6)$$

where A_i and k_i depends on the time constants of particular generating unit.

Substituting Eq. (6) into Eq. (2) leads to Eq. (7):

$$P(t) = -\frac{1}{R} \int_0^t f(x) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n A_i \cdot e^{k_i \cdot (t-x)} dx \quad (7)$$

The determination of $P(t)$ requires knowledge of an explicit representation of the frequency function in the time domain. The explicit function of frequency is usually unknown. It was shown in [29] that

frequency can be approximated with an exponential damped sinusoid function or with the parabolic function [30]. Nevertheless, since the power response at the early stages of frequency fall is of particular interest in this context, the frequency function can be approximated by a linear function with a slope equivalent to the Rate of Change of Frequency (ROCOF), as denoted by Eq. (8):

$$f(t) = a \cdot t + b \quad (8)$$

The value of the parameter a represents the initial ROCOF, while the parameter b can be set to 0, as it characterizes the frequency deviation just prior to the occurrence of the disturbance at time $t = 0$. The functions $P(t)$ are plotted for various generating units and shown in Fig. 2. The values of the time constants utilized in the analysis are typical and can be found in various literature sources [28]. The assumed value for ROCOF was 0.1 Hz/s and for droop coefficient $R = 0.05$.

As depicted in Fig. 2, the hydroelectric plant exhibits a reverse power response [31] and a notable delay of nearly 2 s before it starts to generate power, attributable to the inherent inertia of water [32]. In contrast, a thermal power plant equipped with a reheat turbine requires roughly 1 s to attain 5 % power, whereas the response time for a thermal power plant equipped with a non-reheat turbine is notably faster compared to the other two power plants. Considering the additional time required for the disturbance to propagate through the interconnection line (which is proportional to its length), which can reach up to 1.5 s as evidenced in the literature [4–7], the total time elapsed from the disturbance occurrence before power plants can adequately respond to power changes is approximately 2.5 s on average. This delay can be used to enhance the preparedness of power plants to respond more swiftly to future disturbance events.

3. Proposed primary frequency control mechanism for interconnected power systems

In interconnected power systems, primary frequency control (PFC) and secondary frequency control (SFC) are used to observe frequency control (FC). PFC is responsible for preventing the frequency drop, avoiding under-frequency load shedding, and restoring the frequency to a quasi-steady-state frequency value. SFC restores the frequency to its

Fig. 3. Values of parameter k .

nominal value and regulates the tie-line power flow. This paper proposes a novel PFC reconfiguration method while leaving the SFC mechanism unchanged. The method proposed can be divided into two distinct phases. The first phase, which lasts for the initial few seconds after the disturbance, involves a modified PFC concept. The second phase follows the standard mechanism of frequency control, and the only requirement is to determine the appropriate time for switching between the two phases.

3.1. The first phase – Conventional power systems

As previously elaborated, synchronous generators require a few seconds to respond to changes in frequency, so the proposed method involves initiating the power change process of synchronous generators before the corresponding area's frequency starts to change. To achieve this, turbine governors of synchronous generators located in other areas are provided with the frequency deviation signal of the area in which the disturbance initially occurred. However, to prevent an increase of frequency above 50 Hz in distant areas, where generators start to change power before a physical lack of power is felt, the frequency deviation signal is adjusted using a parameter k to control the desired response rate. The power change of synchronous generators can be expressed as Eq. (9):

$$\Delta P(t) = \frac{1}{R} k \cdot \Delta f_{area-dist}(t) \quad (9)$$

where $\Delta P(t)$ is a generator power change, R is a droop constant, k is a response adjustment parameter, a $\Delta f_{area-dist}(t)$ is a frequency deviation of an area in which disturbance initially occurred.

The parameter k can be determined to prevent sudden excess power from occurring knowing that the generation-demand imbalance in the area where the disturbance did not initially occur is solely evidenced due to changes in power flows through the tie-line. A tie-line bias control approach, which is a widely adopted approach in large interconnections, is implemented. In that type of control, all power systems areas contribute to regulating frequency and interconnector power flow, irrespective of the source of the frequency variation. This behavior is mathematically expressed by the following in Eq. (10):

$$\Delta P_{tie-line}(t) = 2\pi \cdot T_{line} \cdot \int (\Delta f_{area1}(t) - \Delta f_{area2}(t)) dt \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta P_{tie-line}(t)$ is a tie-line power change, T_{line} is a tie-line power coefficient or synchronizing coefficient, $\Delta f_{area}(t)$ is a frequency deviation of a corresponding area.

The following equations were derived assuming that the disturbance takes place in Area 1. Additionally, for simplicity, it is assumed that only one power plant is in operation in Area 2. Therefore, the power change for Area 2 can be expressed as Eq. (11):

power plant power change \leq tie line power change

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ -\frac{1}{R} \Delta f_2(s) \cdot H(s) \right\} &\leq \Delta P_{tie-line}(t) \\ &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ (\Delta f_2(s) - \Delta f_1(s)) \frac{2\pi \cdot T_{line}}{s} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Now, according to the proposed method, at the initial moments, a power plant receives the frequency deviation signal from the disturbed area. Consequently, the frequency change in Area 2 occurs according to the following expression (12):

$$\Delta f_2(s) = \left(-\frac{1}{R} k \cdot \Delta f_1(s) \cdot H(s) \right) \cdot \frac{1}{2H_2 \cdot s + D} \quad (12)$$

where H_2 is an inertia constant of Area 2 and D is a load damping constant. Finally, substituting Eq. (12) into Eq. (11), Eq. (13) is obtained:

$$\mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ -\frac{1}{R} k \cdot \Delta f_1(s) \cdot H(s) \right\} \leq \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ \left(\frac{-\frac{1}{R} k \cdot \Delta f_1(s) \cdot H(s)}{2H_2 \cdot s + D} - \Delta f_1(s) \right) \frac{2\pi \cdot T_{line}}{s} \right\} \quad (13)$$

Given that a primary concern observed in this paper is the initial phase of the frequency response, here it can be once more assumed that the frequency change follows Eq. (8). It's worth noting that assuming a constant slope for the frequency change is the most unfavorable scenario. While generation rate constraint (GRC) does not affect Eq. (13) directly, as the initial power change in the first second can be accommodated by the instantaneous power production of thermal power plants, the governor dead-band (GDB) settings does influence Eq. (13). Power plants do not respond until the frequency deviation surpasses the ± 30 mHz threshold. To address this, Eq. (8), which represents the frequency function, is appropriately modified to reflect this influence, as denoted by Eq. (14):

Fig. 4. The comprehensive illustration of the proposed PFC mechanism designed for a two-area power system.

$$f(t) = a \cdot \left(t + \frac{0.03}{a} \right) \mu \left(t + \frac{0.03}{a} \right) \quad (14)$$

where $\mu(t)$ is Heaviside step function. By employing the Heaviside step function, the frequency signal is effectively set to zero until it surpasses the GDB limit, which in this case is 0.03 Hz (0.03/50 p.u.)

The values of parameter k for a thermal power plant with a reheat turbine and a non-reheat turbine are presented in Fig. 3. As expected, the non-reheat turbine requires smaller values of k due to its faster dynamics compared to the reheat turbine. Fig. 3 displays the maximum values of k necessary due to the assumption of a constant-slope frequency drop in Area 1. The values of k are determined considering the exact amount of power needed from the production units to compensate for the tie-line power flow change. However, to avoid a situation where the production units generate more power than is the change in tie-line power flow,

as that would result in a frequency rise above 50 Hz in that area, the safe zone was defined. It refers to the upper limit of the coefficient k that ensures the power produced by the units does not exceed a certain threshold necessary to match the tie-line power change. Therefore, the identified coefficient k that ensures the production units supply of exactly the required amount of power can be reduced by 10 % as a precautionary measure to prevent frequency rise. The reduction of coefficients k can also account for uncertainties in the time constants of the production units, which Eq. (13) relies upon. The hydroelectric plant case is not included in Fig. 3 as no k value exists that satisfies Eq. (13) due to the hydropower plant reverse effect visible on Fig. 2 as the initial power decrease. Eq. (13) is an expression for the simplified case of only one power plant in the system. In the case of a power generation mix, which is a realistic situation, the generalized form of Eq. (13) should be used, as denoted by Eq. (15):

$$\mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ \Delta f_1(s) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n -\frac{1}{R_i} \cdot k_i \cdot H_i(s) \right\} \leq \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ \left(\frac{\Delta f_1(s) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n -\frac{1}{R_i} \cdot k_i \cdot H_i(s)}{2H_2 \cdot s + D} - \Delta f_1(s) \right) \frac{2\pi \cdot T_{line}}{s} \right\} \quad (15)$$

where n is the number of generators in system.

It should be noted that in order to determine the coefficients k , it is essential to have the parameters H and D , as indicated by Eq. (15). While estimating these parameters with high precision can be challenging, they can generally be constrained within relatively narrow ranges with reasonable effort. For example, the inertia constant H for many synchronous generators typically falls between $H = 3$ s to $H = 7$ s, and the load damping constant D in power systems typically ranges from $D = 0$ to $D = 2$ p.u. [26]. As mentioned earlier, to address potential uncertainties in power system parameters, the coefficients k can be computed using the maximum parameter values and then reduced by 10 %. This approach ensures a robust calculation of the coefficients and considers variations in H and D within their typical ranges.

Additionally, it is important to note that the values of parameters k can vary with operating conditions, depending on the number and type of power plants in operation at a given moment. However, this variability poses no issue for the proposed method. The planning of when and which specific power plants come in or go out of operation is a routine task for Transmission System Operators (TSOs). Consequently, the coefficients k can be pre-calculated for each planned unit commitment in a day-ahead manner and adjusted as needed to account for changes in power plant operations throughout the day.

3.2. The first phase – Future power systems

In the future, power systems are expected to shift towards a higher share of renewable energy sources (RES), particularly hydropower plants, and converter technologies such as battery energy storage system (BESS) and photovoltaic power plants. However, the specific initial response of hydroelectric power plants renders the proposed frequency control method ineffective in systems comprising solely of hydropower plants. Nevertheless, the proposed method can be adapted to include inverter connected RES, given that the latter can participate in frequency control. Converter technologies have already shown their efficacy in primary frequency control. As previously cited, the Hornsdale batteries played a crucial role in restoring frequency stability during a disturbance in Australia [8]. Similarly, a 300 MW PV system in California was highly effective in supporting frequency regulation during an experimental test [33]. By utilizing the rapid response of converter technologies, the proposed method aims to compensate for power changes on the tie-line in the first few seconds following a disturbance. Consequently, the power change of the BESS, for instance, can be calculated according to the following expression (16).

$$\Delta P_{BESS}(s) = 2\pi \cdot T_{line} \cdot \frac{\Delta f(s) - \Delta f_{area-dist}(s)}{s} \cdot BESS(s) \quad (16)$$

where $BESS(s)$ stands for BESS transfer function which is usually represented as a first-order transfer function with a small time constant [34]. By compensating for power changes on the tie-line, the BESS can prolong the frequency drop in distant area while allowing the hydro plants to prepare for the negative power change phase. This enables the hydro plants to promptly respond when the frequency actually begins its drop in that area.

3.3. The second phase – Future power systems

At a certain point when the frequency in Area 2 starts to drop, it becomes necessary to revert the frequency regulation back to the standard mechanism. This ensures the complete effectiveness of the proposed method without necessitating any modifications to the existing settings of the secondary frequency control mechanism. Furthermore, this results in an equitable distribution of the load among generators, which is the key objective of frequency regulation. To prevent abrupt changes in the input signal to turbine controllers, the transition from the initial modified PFC phase to the second standard PFC phase occurs

Fig. 5. The flowchart of the proposed methodology.

when the frequency deviations in both areas are equalized, as determined by the following expression represented by Eq. (17):

$$k \cdot \Delta f_1(t) = \Delta f_2(t) \quad (17)$$

where $\Delta f_1(t)$ is the frequency deviation in disturbed Area 1, and $\Delta f_2(t)$ is the frequency deviation in distant Area 2.

Fig. 4 depicts the schematic representation of the novel proposed PFC algorithm for a power system consisting of two interconnected areas. The control algorithm of the proposed method determines the occurrence of the disturbance and its location by comparing the ROCOF values. While accurately measuring ROCOF presents a notable challenge, it is imperative to emphasize that the primary research focus of this study does not centre on ROCOF measurement methodologies. Any suitable approach for ROCOF measurement can be applied. Furthermore, the method does not require highly precise ROCOF values; rather, the focus is in comparing ROCOF values between different areas. In an interconnected power system, a high ROCOF value will only be detected in the area where the disturbance occurred, while in other areas, due to the propagation of waves, ROCOF will be sensed with some delay and at a lower value. Consequently, comparing ROCOF values at the initial moment should not pose significant challenges. Fig. 4 does not indicate the exact location of the ROCOF measurement since ROCOF can be measured at various points within a particular area. Additionally, with the increasing use of PMUs in power systems and specific areas, ROCOF can be measured at every PMU location within a given area. These values can then be compared to obtain more reliable information about the disturbance.

In the rare case of incorrectly determining disturbance area, two scenarios are considered. If areas are closely interconnected, with

Fig. 6. Single-line diagram of the case-study power system.

minimal distance between them, the proposed method has limited impact on frequency improvement because both areas have nearly identical frequencies. If the areas are distant, and a false disturbance occurs, though the probability of this event being low, the proposed method may initially be less efficient than a conventional frequency control mechanism. However, it is crucial to highlight that the proposed method has been designed to seamlessly transition to the conventional method at a certain point, ensuring that operation continues without any disruption.

According to Fig. 4, generators in the area where the disturbance occurred continue to participate in PFC using the conventional droop method, while in other areas, the PFC mechanism is reconfigured to the proposed mechanism as previously described. Therefore, it is important to highlight that the method developed alters the frequency control approach solely in the area where the disturbance did not take place. Meanwhile, in the area where the initial disturbance occurred, generators continue to participate in frequency regulation using the standard PFC mechanism. It should be noted that the parameters k_1 to k_n represent the response adjustment parameters for power plants in Area 1, while the parameters p_1 to p_n represent the response adjustment parameters for power plants in Area 2. In addition, a flowchart shown in Fig. 5 visually illustrates the proposed controller methodology. This visual representation serves to improve the clarity and readability of the method.

4. Results

A two-area multi-machine power system was used to test the proposed method's efficiency. Fig. 6 displays the power system's schematic diagram, where both areas consist of conventional synchronous generators - hydropower and thermal power plants. The capacity size of Area 1 is 1000 MW, and Area 2 is 800 MW. The tie-line length is 300 km with a transmission capacity of 200 MW. The full-order turbine models (Eq. (3), (4), and (5)) represent the models of hydropower and thermal power plants. Table 1 in the Appendix A provides the parameters for all the elements. In addition, GDB and GRC nonlinearities are incorporated in the model with the following settings. The GDB was set to a typical range of ± 30 mHz, while the GRC was assigned specific values based on different types of power plants [35].

- Thermal power plant with reheat turbine: 5 % puMW per minute;
- Thermal power plant with non-reheat turbine: 10 % puMW per minute;
- Hydropower plant: 100 % puMW per minute.

Additionally, the thermal power plants were modelled to have the ability to instantaneously produce 10 % of their nominal power.

Fig. 7. The frequency in Area 2 for conventional FC (red) and proposed FC (dashed blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. The power response of synchronous generators in Area 2 for conventional FC (red) and proposed FC (dashed blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

4.1. Case study 1 – Conventional power system

In this case study, the PFC mechanism implemented in a conventional power system is analyzed. To simulate the system frequency response to a step load disturbance in Area 1 of the power system, it is first necessary to determine the parameters k for the generating units in Area 2. By referring to Eq. (15), the expression for the parameters k for $t = 1$ s is obtained, as denoted by Eq. (18). A comprehensive derivation of Eq. (18) is presented in the Appendix B.

$$0.31 \cdot k_1 - 1.11 \cdot k_2 - 0.89 \cdot k_3 = -3.14 \tag{18}$$

The parameter k_1 is associated with a hydroelectric power plant, k_2 with a thermal power plant with a non-reheat turbine, and k_3 with a thermal power plant with a reheat turbine. The expression shows that the parameter k_1 acts in the opposite direction of the parameters k_2 and k_3 , precisely because of the already mentioned reverse characteristic of the hydroelectric power plant response in the initial moments. There are various possible combinations of k parameter values, but for this case, the following values were chosen and reduced by 10 %, as denoted by equations Eq. (19)-(21):

$$k_1 = 90\% \cdot 0.4 = 0.36 \tag{19}$$

$$k_2 = 90\% \cdot 0.86 = 0.77 \tag{20}$$

$$k_3 = 90\% \cdot 2.6 = 2.34 \tag{21}$$

The procedure for determining the values of k_1 , k_2 and k_3 is provided in Appendix C.

The system frequency response was simulated for a step load disturbance of $P_{L1} = 0.05$ p.u. at time $t = 2$ s in Area 1 of the case-study power system. While the proposed method has no effect on the frequency in Area 1, where the disturbance occurred, due to the unchanged PFC mechanism for generating units in that area, it demonstrated significant advantages in Area 2 where the conventional droop-based PFC mechanism was replaced by the proposed method.

The frequency response of Area 2 improved, with a lower frequency deviation from the nominal value of $\Delta f = 0.06$ Hz, as shown in Fig. 7. This improvement corresponds to a 15 % reduction in frequency nadir. This implies that in the event of the frequency dropping to

Fig. 9. Modified Area 1 power system.

approximately 49 Hz, the potential improvement could reach up to 0.2 Hz meaning that drop to 48,8 Hz would be avoided. The proposed method's efficacy is attributed to the prolongation of the moment of frequency drop by $t = 1$ s, resulting in a significant reduction in frequency nadir. About 2.5 to 3 s after the disturbance, according to Eq. (17), the algorithm switched to conventional PFC and continued to operate in that mode (Fig. 7). The comparison of frequency responses between the conventional droop method and the proposed method in Area 2 demonstrated the superiority of the proposed novel PFC framework.

A comparison of the synchronous generators power response in Area 2 using the conventional droop method and the proposed method for PFC is shown in Fig. 8. The implementation of the proposed PFC

Fig. 10. The frequency in Area 1 (distanced from the disturbance location) for conventional FC (red) and proposed FC (dashed blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 11. The frequency in Area 2 (location of the disturbance occurrence) for conventional FC (red) and proposed FC (dashed blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

mechanism provided synchronous generators in Area 2 with an additional time of almost one second to increase their production and counteract the frequency drop. This means that the turbine regulators of the synchronous generators received a signal to activate the increase in their power output one second before the frequency actually began to drop.

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 illustrate that the frequency in the quasi-steady-state (Fig. 7) and the total power produced (Fig. 8) in Area 2 remain unchanged when using the proposed PFC method compared to the

conventional PFC method. This indicates that the SFC mechanism does not require any modifications in the proposed method, allowing the standard secondary frequency control procedures to be followed for the remaining frequency control process duration.

4.2. Case study 2 – Future power system

In order to assess the effectiveness of the method on the future power system, it is necessary to make modifications to the system depicted in

Fig. 12. The power response of synchronous generators in Area 1 for conventional FC (red) and proposed FC (dashed blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 13. The BESS power response and tie-line power change during PFC.

Fig. 6. In line with global initiatives aimed at reducing CO₂ levels and increasing production from renewable energy sources, Area 1 was modified as follows: the thermal power plant with a reheat turbine was removed, while the capacity of the thermal power plant with a non-reheat turbine was reduced to 50 MW and the hydropower plant capacity was increased to 800 MW. A 100 MW capacity photovoltaic (PV) power plant and a 50 MW capacity battery energy storage system (BESS) were introduced to the system. The modified Area 1 system is illustrated in Fig. 9.

The simulations were carried out with the assumption that the BESS is capable of participating in frequency control, while the PV system does not participate in frequency control. Under the conventional PFC mechanism, the BESS participates in frequency control through the droop-based approach, whereas in the proposed PFC mechanism, the BESS contributes to frequency control according to Eq. (16) to modify

the power generation in response to the tie-line power change. According to Eq. (15) in this case, coefficient $k_1 = 0.9$ and $k_2 = 1.3$ were determined. The system frequency response was simulated for a step load disturbance of $P_{L2} = 0.05$ p.u. at time $t = 2$ s in Area 2.

Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 present a comparison between the frequency response of Area 1 and Area 2 under the conventional PFC method and the proposed PFC method, respectively. In this case as well, a considerable improvement in frequency response is noticeable, specifically in terms of frequency nadir in Area 1 where disturbance did not occur, as shown in Fig. 10. However, in Area 2, where the disturbance occurs, there is no significant change in the frequency response, as shown in Fig. 11. This is because generators in that area continue to operate using the conventional PFC method. Through the implementation of the BESS, the initial negative response of the hydropower plants was neutralized, and the frequency drop was prolonged by approximately 1 s. In this

Table 1
Power system model parameters.

Parameters	Area 1			Area 2		
	HPP	TPP_reheat	TPP_non-reheat	HPP	TPP_reheat	TPP_non-reheat
Nominal power	600 MW	200 MW	200 MW	400 MW	300 MW	100 MW
Inertia constant H	5 s	7 s	6 s	5 s	4 s	6 s
Droop $R_{H,T}$	5 %	5 %	4 %	6 %	4 %	5 %
Governor time constant T_G	0.3 s	0.2 s	0.2 s	0.2 s	0.2 s	0.2 s
Reset time T_R	7 s	–	–	5 s	–	–
Transient droop R_T	0.5 s	–	–	0.38 s	–	–
Turbine time constant T_W	1.05 s	–	–	1 s	–	–
Reheater time constant T_{RH}	–	7 s	–	–	7 s	–
Control valve time constant T_{CH}	–	0.25 s	0.3 s	–	0.3 s	0.30 s
Fraction of the power in the high-pressure steam turbine F_{HP}	–	0.35	–	–	0.3	–

simulation, the HPP and TPP switched to the standard droop method after about 2 s, hence the frequency response following the frequency nadir is comparable to that of the conventional PFC method.

In Fig. 12, a comparison of power response from HPP and from TPP reveals a considerably more prominent reverse power response from the hydropower plant in the proposed PFC method. By compensating the tie-line power change with BESS, the hydropower plant is capable of responding more promptly without substantially affecting the frequency in that area. As a result, when there is an actual frequency drop in Area 1, the hydropower plant has already completed its negative response phase and is prepared to provide a positive response to counteract the frequency drop.

Due to its faster dynamics compared to tie-line power changes, BESS can easily adjust its power output according to changes in tie-line power flow. However, the power capacity of BESS is typically much smaller than that of the transmission lines, which limits their ability to track the dynamics of tie-line power changes, as illustrated in Fig. 13. In the case examined, the BESS had a power capacity of 50 MW, while the tie-line power capacity can typically be several hundred megawatts. Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 13, at some point, the BESS switched to the standard droop mechanism according to the algorithm scheme shown in Fig. 4. Thus, after a few seconds following the disturbance, the BESS operated independently of the tie-line power change.

The results demonstrate that the proposed method enhances frequency control. However, it's important to emphasize that the paper does not conduct a cost and economic analysis, as this falls outside its scope. The key difference from conventional frequency control is that some generators begin contributing to frequency control slightly earlier. While this may incur slightly higher costs due to earlier power adjustments, it also prevents a greater frequency decline, leading to faster recovery and potentially lower total energy production. Moreover, reducing or avoiding the potential consequences and energy not served amounts also provides a valuable justification for the application of this method which results in cost savings. Therefore, conducting a cost analysis in this context is complex and not straightforward.

5. Conclusion

This paper introduces a new PFC framework for interconnected power systems that can be used in both conventional and future power systems. The proposed method aims to develop a mechanism that allows generators in areas distant from disturbance location to respond to

Appendix A

Table 1

Appendix B

The left side of Eq. (15) can be rewritten as follows:

frequency changes more quickly by passing real-time data to them using the PMUs. The method was tested using a typical two-area power system model. Compared to the conventional droop method for PFC, the proposed method's primary benefit is the notable reduction in frequency nadir in these distant areas. It is highlighted that the proposed method resulted in a 15 % reduction in the maximum frequency deviation from the nominal value. During the load disturbance event of 0.05 p.u., the proposed method resulted in an improvement of 0.06 Hz in the frequency nadir. Furthermore, in scenarios where the frequency dropped to approximately 49 Hz, the potential improvement could lead to a higher frequency nadir of up to 0.2 Hz. An additional advantage of the proposed method is that it does not require any modifications to the existing secondary frequency control, which can continue to operate based on conventional settings. Overall, the proposed PFC framework offers an effective solution to the issue of time delay in power system disturbances and reduces the frequency nadir in distant areas, improving the stability of the interconnected power system. In addition, this paper can provide a foundation for future modifications of PFC as converter-based generation technologies continue to be integrated into power systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tomislav Baškarad: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Ninoslav Holjevac:** Writing – original draft, Software, Validation. **Igor Kuzle:** Writing – review & editing, Validation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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$$\mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ \Delta f_1(s) \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{R_{HPP}} \cdot k_1 \cdot H_{HPP}(s) - \frac{1}{R_{TPP_nr}} \cdot k_2 \cdot H_{TPP_nr}(s) - \frac{1}{R_{TPP_rt}} \cdot k_3 \cdot H_{TPP_rt}(s) \right) \right\}$$

where $H_{HPP}(s)$, $H_{TPP_nr}(s)$ and $H_{TPP_rt}(s)$ are the transfer functions of generating units given in Eqs. (3)-(5). Considering the parameters of the power plants provided in the Appendix A, in Table 1, these transfer functions can be expressed as follows:

$$H_{HPP}(s) = \frac{1}{1+0.2s} \cdot \frac{1+5s}{1+38s} \cdot \frac{1-s}{1+0.5s}$$

$$H_{TPP_nr}(s) = \frac{1}{1+0.2s} \cdot \frac{1+2.1s}{(1+0.3s)(1+7s)}$$

$$H_{TPP_rt}(s) = \frac{1}{1+0.2s} \cdot \frac{1}{(1+0.3s)}$$

The values of R_{HPP} , R_{TPP_nr} , and R_{TPP_rt} which are also listed in Table 1, should be presented in per-unit values based on the power system base power. Taking this into consideration, the following values are derived:

$$R_{HPP} = \frac{0.4}{0.06}, R_{TPP_nr} = \frac{0.1}{0.04}, R_{TPP_rt} = \frac{0.3}{0.04}$$

The Laplace transform of Eq. (14) allows to determine $\Delta f_1(s)$, with the parameter 'a' calculated as follows:

$a = \Delta P/2H_2$, where ΔP represents the analyzed disturbance size in per-unit and H_2 stands for the inertia constant of Area 2.

$$\Delta f_1(s) = \frac{-0.01 \cdot e^{-0.06s}}{s^2}$$

Upon substituting all these values into the left side of Eq. (15) and applying the inverse Laplace transform, one obtains the following result for $t = 1$. It's worth noting that computational software is typically used for this process.

$$-0.003769 \cdot k_1 + 0.01179 \cdot k_2 + 0.009511 \cdot k_3$$

For the right side of Eq. (15), the only missing values are for D and T_{line} . In this particular case, it was assumed that the parameter D is set to 0 and T_{line} is considered to be 1.27 p.u. When applying the inverse Laplace transform to the right side of Eq. (15), for $t = 1$ the result is:

$$-0.000627 \cdot k_1 + 0.000657 \cdot k_2 + 0.000552 \cdot k_3 + 0.031443$$

Finally, Eq. (18) is derived:

$$-0.003769 \cdot k_1 + 0.01179 \cdot k_2 + 0.009511 \cdot k_3 = -0.000627 \cdot k_1 + 0.000657 \cdot k_2 + 0.000552 \cdot k_3 + 0.031443$$

$$0.31 \cdot k_1 - 1.11 \cdot k_2 - 0.89 \cdot k_3$$

Appendix C

When determining the values for k_1 , k_2 and k_3 in Eq. 18, it is crucial to consider the Generation Rate Constraint (GRC), as these parameters directly influence power plant production. For example, the parameter k_1 , linked to the hydropower plant, may be constrained in the following manner:

$$k_1 \cdot \Delta f_{area1} \cdot \frac{1}{R_{HPP}} \cdot P_{HPP} < GRC$$

Given that Eq. 18 is derived for $t = 1$ s, the corresponding GRC value for 1 s is calculated as 400 MW/60 s = 6.66 MW/s:

$$k_1 \cdot \frac{50 - 49.92}{50} \cdot \frac{1}{0.06} \cdot \frac{400}{1000} < \frac{6.66}{1000}$$

The expression above requires the use of a per-unit value. The calculation of the aforementioned expression results in:

$$k_1 < 0.62$$

Similarly, the values of k_2 and k_3 can be constrained to be less than 3. However, in this scenario, the GRC should consider the thermal power plant's capacity to instantaneously produce 10 % of its nominal power.

The parameter k_1 acts in the opposite direction of the parameters k_2 and k_3 because of the reverse characteristic of the hydroelectric power plant response in the initial moments, thus it does not actively contribute to power generation. Consequently, only thermal power plants are taken into account for power production. Considering that a thermal power plant with a reheat turbine has three times the nominal power of a thermal power plant with a non-reheat turbine, the coefficient k_3 can be set three times larger than k_2 to enhance power generation from the larger power plant.

$$3 \cdot k_2 = k_3$$

$$0.31 \cdot k_1 - 1.11 \cdot k_2 - 0.89 \cdot (3 \cdot k_2) = -3.14$$

$$0.31 \cdot k_1 - 3.78 \cdot k_2 = -3.14$$

To meet the limit derived above, a value lower than 0.62 can be assigned to k_1 . In this instance, a value of $k_1 = 0.4$ was selected.

$$0.31 \cdot 0.4 - 3.78 \cdot k_2 = -3.14$$

$$k_2 = 0.866$$

$$k_3 = 3 \cdot 0.866 = 2.6$$

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